

Research Article

Growth and Carcass Characteristics of Broiler Chickens fed Acha-Based Diet Supplemented With Phytase® Enzyme

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Abstract

This study evaluated the growth and carcass of broiler chickens fed acha diet supplemented with phytase® enzyme. Acha grains were used as replacement for maize such that two basal diets were formulated; maize-soybean and acha-soybean to serve as positive (T₁) and negative (T₂) control groups, respectively. The phytase® enzyme was supplemented into the acha-based diet only at 250, 500 and 750mg/kg to constitute treatments T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively. A total of one hundred and twenty (120), day-old Abor-Acre broiler chicks were assigned to the five treatments with 24 birds each using a completely randomized design (CRD). Each treatment was further sub - divided into three replicates of seven (8) birds each. All chicks were managed in a deep litter house under the same experimental conditions for 49 days. Data was collected on the growth performance, carcass characteristics and organoleptic properties of chicken breast muscles. Results showed significant (P<0.05) differences in all growth parameters (except the feed conversion ratio) between dietary treatments. Final body weight, weight gain, feed intake and feed conversion ratio improved with enzyme supplementation. Feed intake was enhanced for birds fed acha with or without enzyme supplementation. Cost per kg gain, cost of feed consumed per bird and weekly cost of feed were significantly (P<0.05) influenced by dietary treatments. Phytase supplementation slightly improved the carcass yield (75.21 - 75.85%) of broiler chickens. Relative weights for back and breast weight were significantly (P<0.05) affected

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by dietary treatments. Generally, relative organ weights showed significant ($P < 0.05$) difference for full gizzard, empty gizzard, proventriculus and oesophagus. Organoleptic properties of the breast muscle showed significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between dietary treatments and cooking methods. The study concludes that acha - based diet supplemented with phytase enzyme for broiler chickens has shown some produce positive responses in growth performance and carcass characteristics.

Key Words: Acha, phytase, performance, chickens

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Introduction

Cereals and legumes form a significant portion of the food supply for humans and animals, as they are major sources of carbohydrates, proteins, lipids and minerals (Katina *et al.*, 2005). In the tropics, maize is the most utilized cereal in the animal feed industry and its future utilization is hampered by its growing global demand for industrial uses and attendant high cost. Cadoni and Angelucci (2013) identified high cost of feeds as the major obstacle militating against rapid expansion of the poultry industry in developing countries. Barletta (2010) further noted that feed is the most expensive cost item accounting for over 60% of the total production cost in poultry production. Therefore, extant researches should focus on the exploration of locally; available, cheaper alternative feed resources that can replace the expensive conventional cereals (Ukim *et al.*, 2013; Ozung *et al.*, 2016). One of such alternative feedstuffs is Acha (*Digitaria iburua*).

Acha commonly called black fonio is an indigenous cereal of West Africa dating back to 7,000 years (Cruz *et al.*, 2011). *Digitaria iburua* belongs to the family *Graminae*, tribe - *Poaceae* and closely related to the wild species - *Digitaria longiflora*. In Nigeria, acha is mainly grown in Plateau, Bauchi, Kebbi, Taraba, Kaduna and Niger States where it serves as staple food for man. Aside Nigeria, acha is also widely cultivated in parts of Sierra Leone, Guinea and Togo.

Acha is also called "hungry man" rice as it is perceived as the food for the poor probably due to its unique small grains (Cruz *et al.*, 2011). Nevertheless, it has comparable nutritional qualities to most grains. Acha grain has crude protein content

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(5.75 – 12%), total ash (1.08 – 5.70%), crude fat (3.35 – 6.49%) and crude fibre (0.41 - 11.3) (Cruz *et al.*, 2011), carbohydrate (67.24 – 83.38%) with gross energy (3,556.06 – 3,786.4kcal/kg) (Cruz *et al.*, 2011; Ukim *et al.*, 2013). According to NAS (1996), the amino acid profile of acha is comparable to that of whole-egg protein and it is a rich source of minerals including magnesium, zinc, iron and manganese.

However, the presence of anti-nutrients such as phytate has been a major limiting factor to the extensive utilization of acha (Al-Numair *et al.*, 2009; Azeke *et al.*, 2011). Anuonye *et al.* (2010) also reported that acha grain is of low toxicity with moderate amounts of antinutrients. Phytate, (myo-inositol 1, 2, 3,4,5,6 hexakisphosphate), is present in high concentrations in many food items derived from plants. It is the major storage form of phosphorus in mature grains and legumes (Kumar *et al.*, 2010). Its hydrolysis is catalyzed by the enzyme phytase (myoinositol hexaphosphate phosphohydrolase) to inositol and orthophosphate. About 60–90% of total phosphorus in plant feedstuffs is bound as phytate phosphorus (Wu *et al.*, 2009). Phosphorus, in this form, is not utilized by humans or birds because they lack sufficient endogenous intestinal phytase which releases orthophosphate from the phytate molecule in the gastrointestinal tract (Holm *et al.*, 2002). The unabsorbed phytate is excreted and contributes to phosphate pollution in water bodies downstream of agriculturally intensive areas (Sharpley, 1999).

Phytate also acts in a broad pH-region as a highly negatively charged ion and therefore its presence in the diet has a negative impact on the bioavailability of divalent and trivalent mineral ions such as Zn^{2+} , $Fe^{2+}/^{3+}$, Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Cu^{2+} (Wu *et al.*, 2009). The need to maintain sufficient dietary phosphorus levels while reducing phosphorus excretion in poultry manure has led to an increase in the application of phytase to poultry feeds (Hatten *et al.*, 2001; Cowieson and Adeola, 2005; Cowieson and Ravindran, 2008; Leytem *et al.*, 2008; Olukosi *et al.*, 2010).

The use of phytase reduces phosphorus excretion in poultry manure by allowing the birds to utilize more of the phytate phosphorus (Sharpley, 1999). Phytase also frees cations and proteases bound in phytate phosphorus complexes and improve many production parameters and body structure characteristics in broilers and laying hens, such as body weight, bone ash content, feed consumption, egg weight, and egg shell quality (Hatten *et al.*, 2001). The increase in phytase activity is known to be accompanied by a significant reduction in phytate and a small but significant increase in total phosphorus (Azeke *et al.*, 2011). Several studies have shown positive effects of phytase supplementations on broilers fed corn (Olukosi *et al.*, 2007; 2010; Cowieson and Ravindran, 2008), wheat (Barrier-Guillot *et al.*, 1996), rice (Azeke *et al.*, 2011) and white

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bean (Al-Numair *et al.*, 2009) and barley based diets. However, there is dearth of information on the use of phytase in improving acha utilization by broiler chickens. This study therefore evaluated the efficacy of phytase supplementation on the growth, carcass and organoleptic characteristics of broiler chickens fed acha-based diet.

Materials and Methods

Location of study

This study was carried out at the Poultry Unit of the University of Calabar Teaching and Research Farm. Calabar is located between latitude $4^{\circ} 58' N$ and $15^{\circ} 39' N$, longitude $8^{\circ} 17' E$ and $10^{\circ} 43' E$ of the equator with an elevation of 99 meters above sea level. The temperature and rainfall averages are between 25° and $30^{\circ} C$ as well as 1260-3500mm, respectively (Google Earth, 2018).

Experimental materials

The test material used in this study was Acha (*Digitaria exilis*). The unpolished whole 'Acha' (*Digitaria exilis*) grains were purchased from Bogoro Local Government Area, Bauchi State, Nigeria. Thereafter, the grains were manually cleaned by picking the chaffs and stones. Phytase[®] enzyme (Aextra[®] PHY), a product of Danisco Animal Nutrition, DuPont Industrial Biosciences, Marlborough, UK was procured from Agrited Nigeria Ltd. Aextra[®] PHY, a phytase feed grade enzyme, is sourced from a *Buttiauxella* bacterium and is expressed in a *Trichodema reesei* fungus.

Experimental diets

Two basal broiler starter and finisher diets (Table 1) were formulated to provide the required nutrients according to NRC (2012) recommendations.

Table 1: Gross composition of basal diets (%)

Ingredient	Starter diets		Finisher diets	
	Maize-based	Acha-based	Maize-based	Acha-based
Maize	49.25	0.00	50.00	0.00
Acha	0.00	49.25	0.00	50.00
Soybean meal	35.00	35.00	28.75	28.75
Fish meal	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Wheat offal	7.00	7.00	10.00	10.00
Bone meal	3.50	3.50	3.00	3.00
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
PKC	2.00	2.00	5.00	5.00
Vit-Min Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Palm oil	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Methionine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Calculated values				
Crude Protein (%)	22.51	23.99	20.85	22.35
ME (Kcal/kg)	3100.40	3177.53	3041.75	3120.05
Determined CP (%)	23.21	23.61	20.23	21.86

The maize-basal standard diet served as the positive control, while the acha basal diet without phytase® enzyme acted as negative control. To improve the utilization of acha grains by broilers, phytase® enzyme was supplemented at three levels; 250, 500 and 750 mg/kg of acha diets at both the starter and finisher phases. The acha diets were formulated in one batch then subdivided into 4 experimental diets, with three diets containing phytase at three levels (250, 500 and 750 mg/kg of acha diet) each.

The five experimental treatments were as follows;

- T₁: Maize-soybean diet as positive control
- T₂: Acha-soybean diet as negative control
- T₃: Acha-soybean diet plus supplemental Phytase at 250mg/kg
- T₄: Acha-soybean diet plus supplemental Phytase at 500mg/kg
- T₅: Acha-soybean diet plus supplemental Phytase at 750mg/kg

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Management of experimental birds

The chickens were raised under the deep litter system using wood shavings as litter material. Brooding was by means of electricity and kerosene stove as sources of heat. Temperature of the brooding room was controlled by either reducing or increasing the electric bulbs' heights or flame of the stove or outright removal after reading the thermometer. A total of 120, day-old Abor-Acre broiler chicks were used in this study. The birds were randomly distributed into the five experimental treatments consisting of 24 chicks each using a completely randomised design (CRD). Each treatment was further subdivided into three replicates of eight birds each. On arrival, anti-stress vitalityte was provided to the birds via the drinking water. Birds were vaccinated against Newcastle disease on the third day intra ocularly; Lasota on the 14th and 28th days; infectious bursal disease (Gumboro) on the 12th and 19th days, respectively. Birds were controlled against coccidiosis from the 14th - 21st days, and then at the 30th and 35th day. Anti-chronic respiratory disease (CRD) drug was used to protect birds from the 18th day of age for 7 days and later at 30th day of age for 7 days. Vitamins were administered at intervals, especially before and after each vaccination. The experiment lasted for 7 weeks.

Growth performance

Each treatment was assessed based on their body weight, body weight gain, feed intake and feed conversion ratio.

Carcass evaluation

At the end of the experiment (day 49), a total of 30 birds (two/replicates/treatment) were randomly selected, starved overnight and weighed individually before slaughter. The dressed weights were determined. The dressing percentages were calculated, prime cut parts and organ weights were individually measured and expressed as percentages of the live weight.

a.
$$\text{Dressing percentage} = \frac{\text{dressed weight}}{\text{Live weight}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

b. *Prime cuts*

The carcass was dissected into different cuts such as:

- Thigh
- Shank
- Wing
- Drum stick
- Breast

- Back
- Neck
- head

$$c. \text{ Organ weight (\% live weight)} = \frac{\text{Organ weight}}{\text{Live weight}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Gastro-intestinal tract (GIT) morphometry

The effect of the feeds on the GIT morphology was determined through the segmentation of the intestine to determine the weights, lengths and pH of the total intestine, duodenum, jejunum, ileum and caeca. Gastro - intestinal tract was obtained *intoto*, and cleaned of all adhering tissues. Digestive organs (oesophagus, crop, proventriculus, gizzard, liver, kidney, heart, spleen and lungs) were carefully separated and weighed using a sensitive electronic scale (Model- 110C). Organ weight was expressed as percentage of live weight. Total intestinal tract length and weight were measured, segmented (duodenum, jejunum, ileum and caeca) and respective weight and length were measured using a sensitive scale and measuring tape, respectively.

Organoleptic evaluation

Organoleptic properties of experimental broiler meat were evaluated using methods described by Akinnusi and Alade (2011). 300g of meat sample was collected from the breast muscle from each treatment. They were washed thoroughly; 3g of iodized common salt was mixed with the bulk of each 300g meat and thereafter cut into bite sizes (2.50 - 3.00cm) prior to cooking. The meat samples were divided into three portions (100g) and cooked by: boiling, microwaving or oven drying. The first meat portion was boiled at 100°C in a pot for 20 minutes using kerosene stove. An electric micro-wave oven (Matsui model MS-106WH, made in China) was used in cooking the second meat portion for 20 minutes. While, the third meat portion was oven dried at 80°C for 20 minutes using an electric oven (Saisho - toast plus, model S- 909). Following cooking, each meat sample was placed in properly sealed plastic container and labelled according to the treatments and cooking methods, thereafter they were placed in a cooler for about one hour to permit cooling at 20^o - 25^oC (Fabiya, 2005).

During sensory evaluation, the pieces of meat were arranged according to the 11 treatment groups and the three cooking methods. Eleven consumer panelists (25 - 40 years) were selected from the Department of Animal Science, University of Calabar and instructed on the scoring pattern. Each meat sample was evaluated for colour, flavour, juiciness, number of chews, remains after chewing and overall acceptability based on the 4 - point hedonic scale;

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Where;

- 4 = very desirable
- 3 = slightly acceptable
- 2 = unacceptable
- 1 = very unacceptable

The panelists were seated far away from one another in a well lit room during the session to avoid communication. At each successive chewing, panelists chewed cracker biscuit and rinse their mouth with water to prevent carry over effect from the previous sample tasted.

Economic analysis

Cost analysis was carried out at the end of the study period and the gross margin analysis was conducted to determine the profitability of whole acha grains replacement for maize in broiler diets as well as additional benefit of phytase supplementation.

- Cost/kg feed = $\frac{\sum \text{proportion of each ingredient in the diet} \times \text{cost per kg of the ingredient}}{100}$
- Feed cost/bird = Feed consumed x cost/kg feed
- Feed cost/kg live weight = cost/kg feed x feed: gain ratio

Statistical analysis

All data collected were subjected to a one-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for a completely randomized design according to the methods of Steel and Torrie (1980). Significant means were separated using Duncan's New Multiple Range Test of GENSTAT Release 8.1 (GENSTAT, 2011) statistical software package.

Results and Discussion

Growth performance characteristics fed acha - based diets

The result of the growth performance of broilers fed acha-based diet supplemented with phytase is presented in Table 2. Final body weight was significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by dietary treatments. Birds fed 750 mg of phytase with acha-based diet had significantly higher final body weight, although this value was statistically similar with the value recorded for birds on 250 mg and 500 mg of phytase with acha-based diet while those fed maize-based diet had the least (1774.40g). The range of 1774.40 – 2141.67g obtained in this study was lower than the 2155g earlier reported by Dafwang (2006) but were within the range reported by Omojola *et al.* (2014), Afolayan *et al.* (2014)

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and Uchegbu *et al.* (2010) who reported 1557.50 – 2212.50g, 1764 – 2820.37g and 1939.10 – 2022.08g, respectively for broilers at 8 weeks. The final weight obtained showed that birds on diet supplemented with phytase in each of the feeding regimes was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher compared with those on the respective control diets. Average weekly body weight was significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by dietary treatments. Statistically similar values were obtained for birds fed phytase and acha-based diets although birds fed 750 mg of phytase had numerically higher value while those on maize-based diet had the least ($P < 0.05$). Average weekly feed intake was significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by dietary treatments. Birds fed 250 mg of phytase consumed the highest feed while those fed maize-based diet consumed the least. The feed conversion ratio (FCR) although not significantly ($P > 0.05$) different was highest for maize-based diet group. The lower weight gain of birds in the control group could be due to low feed intake. Dietary proteins and amino acid content of the feed, particle size and dietary energy levels could affect feed intake. The results of the present study showed that broiler chickens fed phytase supplemented diets had better performance in terms of weight gain and FCR. Earlier studies (Scott *et al.* 1997; Moshad, 2001 and Aksaka and Bilal, 2002) showed that broiler chickens fed diets supplemented with phytase had improved FCR due to better feed utilization. Similarly, results of this study agreed with the findings (Huff *et al.*, 1998; Namkung and Leeson, 1999; Zyla *et al.*, 1999 and Bozkurt *et al.*, 2006) who reported that the growth rate and FCR of broilers fed low Phosphorus (P) diets containing phytase were comparable or even better than those obtained from broilers fed standard P diets.

These results also agreed with those reported by El-Medany and El-Afif (2002); Arabi, (2006) and El-Tazi *et al.* (2009); which indicated that the body weight gain and feed intake were significantly improved by addition of phytase to broiler diets. The improvement in growth performance of broilers fed phytase supplemented diets could be attributed to the improvement in essential amino acids and metabolizable energy as reported in earlier studies (Ravindran *et al.*, 2000 and Attia *et al.*, 2001) or due to overall increased utilization of nutrients (Miles and Nelson, 1974).

The economic implications of supplementing phytase shows that all the economic indices apart from cost per kg of feed were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by dietary treatments. There was no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference in cost per kg gain between acha-based diet and phytase supplemented diets but cost per kg gain was significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower for maize-based diets group. Although, birds fed 250 mg phytase had numerically higher cost per kg gain. It was further observed that 750 mg of phytase also posted higher feed cost per bird compared to the control diets. Weekly feed cost was

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similar to the trend of cost of feed consumed per bird. Birds fed 250 mg of phytase had higher ($P < 0.05$) weekly feed cost while those fed maize-based diet had the least.

Table 2: Growth performance of broilers fed acha – based diets (0 – 7 weeks)

Parameters	Treatments					SEM
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	
Initial wt.(g/bird)	39.00	39.00	39.00	39.00	39.00	0.00
Final wt.(g/bird)	1774.40 ^b	2002.08 ^{ab}	2105.12 ^a	2096.73 ^a	2141.67 ^a	85.60
Av.weekly wt. gain (g/bird/wk)	247.91 ^b	280.44 ^{ab}	295.16 ^a	293.96 ^a	300.38 ^a	12.23
Av.weekly feed intake (g/bird/wk)	777.71 ^c	818.88 ^{bc}	916.61 ^a	821.12 ^{bc}	893.99 ^{ab}	25.97
FCR	3.14	2.93	3.12	2.80	2.98	0.10
Cost/kg feed(₦)	209.66	327.16	327.19	327.23	327.27	0.00
Cost/kg gain(₦)	657.37 ^b	958.20 ^a	1021.34 ^a	916.61 ^a	974.08 ^a	32.32
Cost of feed(₦) consumed/bird	1141.39 ^c	1875.34 ^b	2099.35 ^a	1880.86 ^b	2048.03 ^{ab}	55.89
Weekly feed cost(₦)	163.06 ^c	267.91 ^b	299.91 ^a	268.69 ^b	292.58 ^{ab}	7.98

^{abc} Means with different superscripts on the same row differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)
SEM = Standard error of mean

Carcass characteristics of broiler chickens fed acha – based diets

Table 3 shows the carcass characteristics of broiler chickens fed dietary treatments. Live weight, dressed weight, weight of prime cuts (back and breast) and organ (full gizzard, empty gizzard, proventriculus and oesophagus) were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by dietary treatments. The Live weight ranging from 1680 – 2300g were obtained in this study which was higher ($P < 0.05$) in birds fed acha with enzymes compared to the maize and acha without enzyme fed birds. Values for live weight obtained in this study were lower than those (2740.00 – 3023.33g) reported by Ukim *et al.* (2012) for broilers fed graded levels of acha grains but comparable to the range 1557.50 – 2212.50g reported by Omojola *et al.* (2014) for broilers fed Sesame/Soybean based diets supplemented with or

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without phytase. Live weight obtained for phytase supplemented diets were comparable to the range 1760 – 2020g and 1996.82 – 2072.93g reported by Afolayan *et al.* (2014) and Ndelekwute *et al.* (2014) for broilers fed African locust bean and Acetic acid-treated diets, respectively. Dressed weight values ranging from 1250 – 1733g were obtained in this study which higher ($P < 0.05$) was for birds fed acha with enzymes compared to maize and acha fed birds. Vejtech *et al.* (2014) however, reported lower dressed weight (1106 – 1380g) for broilers fed Serine protease. The variations in results could be attributed to the duration of the different studies as well as type of diets. The dressing percentage (73.36 – 75.85%) was higher ($P > 0.05$) in birds fed acha with enzymes than those fed maize-based diet and acha-based diet. This is an indication that birds on acha supplemented with enzymes efficiently utilized their nutrients more and converted them to flesh (meat) more than those on the control groups. Dressing percentage in this study was higher than the range (66.89 – 68.98%) reported by Ukim and Obun (2014). However, values obtained in this study were comparable to the range (71.30 – 73.10%) reported by Vejtech *et al.* (2014) for broilers fed graded levels of acha grains and Serine protease, respectively. This result showed that the carcass yield of broilers was not negatively affected when fed acha supplemented diets.

Birds on the maize – based diet had higher ($P < 0.05$) values for major prime cuts (back and breast) weights followed by those on 500 mg of phytase with higher ($P > 0.05$) drumstick, thigh, wings and shanks while acha without enzymes recorded the least weight for drumstick, wings, neck, shank and head. This is an indication that acha without enzyme might not enhance broiler carcass yield. Prime cuts values obtained in this study were not consistent with previous reports (Ukim and Obun 2014; Omojola *et al.*, 2014). The variations may be attributed to the age of the birds at slaughter in the different studies.

Table 3: Carcass characteristics of broiler chickens fed acha – based diets

Parameters	Treatments					SEM
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	
Live wt. /bird(g)	1683.00 ^b	1817.00 ^b	2017.00 ^{ab}	2000.00 ^{ab}	2300.00 ^a	117.60
Dressed wt.(g/bird)	1250.00 ^b	1333.00 ^b	1517.00 ^{ab}	1517.00 ^{ab}	1733.00 ^a	110.60
Dressing %	74.27	73.36	75.21	75.85	75.35	2.38
Prime cuts relative weight (%)						
Back	15.32 ^a	14.44 ^{ab}	13.96 ^{ab}	13.85 ^{ab}	12.22 ^b	0.71
Breast	16.63 ^a	15.37 ^{ab}	14.08 ^{bc}	13.97 ^{bc}	12.24 ^c	0.75
Drumstick	10.76	10.62	10.94	11.24	11.22	0.45
Thigh	12.04	12.89	12.60	12.95	12.02	0.73
Wings	8.87	8.39	9.13	9.47	8.89	0.36
Neck	5.61	5.08	5.42	5.59	5.15	0.25
Shank	3.96	3.63	3.92	4.25	4.00	0.28
Head	2.50	2.31	2.69	2.68	2.20	0.16

^{abc} Means with different superscripts on the same row differ significantly (P<0.05)
SEM = Standard error of means

Internal organs weight of broilers fed acha – based diets

Table 4 revealed that the internal organs (relative weights) of full gizzard, empty gizzard, proventriculus, and oesophagus were significantly (P < 0.05) influenced by dietary treatments. Birds on maize – based diet recorded higher values for heart, full gizzard, empty gizzard, spleen, pancreas and gall bladder compared to those on acha – based diets. Higher heart weight obtained for maize – based diet comparable to those on acha – based diets could be an indication that maize – based diet could maintain the normal circulatory function in broilers. The lower gizzard weight in acha fed birds indicated that digestive process was not impaired by the utilization of acha. The relative organ weights observed were within the ranges previously reported (Odoemelam *et al.*, 2017). The small weights for the digestive organs of birds fed phytase diets was an indication of the better feed efficiency observed as the time it takes for digestion activities will be reduced leading to better nutrient utilization. The range of relative weight of spleen (0.07 – 0.10%) obtained in this study was lower than the range reported by Odoemelam *et al.* (2017) and Aguihe *et al.* (2016) for broilers fed dietary Scent leaf, garlic and antibiotics and those fed Maxi grain enzyme supplemented cassava peel

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meal based diets. The lower relative spleen weight in acha – based supplemented diets could be an indication that immune functions of the birds were not compromised but enhanced by enzyme supplementation. The improvements in the parameters in this present study conform to the earlier assertion of Iyayi and Davis (2005); Adeola and Olukosi (2008) that enzymes supplementation improves performance, carcass and organ characteristics of broiler chickens.

Table 4: Internal organs of broiler chickens fed acha – based diets (relative weight, %)

Parameters	Treatments					SEM
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	
Heart	0.41	0.36	0.38	0.40	0.38	0.03
Liver	1.25	1.75	1.42	1.47	1.33	0.28
Full gizzard	3.17 ^a	2.19 ^b	2.37 ^b	2.42 ^b	2.32 ^b	0.20
Empty gizzard	2.44 ^a	1.40 ^b	1.76 ^b	1.75 ^b	1.76 ^b	0.13
Spleen	0.10	0.10	0.07	0.09	0.07	0.02
Lungs	0.46	0.47	0.50	0.46	0.43	0.04
Proventriculus	0.55 ^{ab}	0.69 ^a	0.43 ^b	0.47 ^b	0.40 ^b	0.06
Pancreas	0.21	0.20	0.18	0.20	0.17	0.03
Oesophagus	0.16 ^{ab}	0.13 ^{abc}	0.12 ^{bc}	0.17 ^a	0.12 ^c	0.01
Crop	0.31	0.30	0.25	0.32	0.24	0.03
Gall bladder	0.16	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.10	0.03
Trachea	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.16	0.12	0.02

^{abc} Means with different superscripts on the same row differ significantly (P<0.05)
SEM = Standard error of means

GIT morphometry of broilers fed acha – based diets

The results of the effect of dietary treatments on the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) morphometry (Table 5) revealed that there were no significant (P > 0.05) effects of dietary treatments on the GIT segments. The non-significant differences further reveal that phytase supplementation had no negative effects on total GIT weight, although birds on 500 mg of phytase had heavier GIT while the least weight was obtained in those fed maize – based diet. Weight of the duodenum, jejunum and ilium were lower for birds on 750 mg of phytase while jejunum and ilium were heavier in those fed acha – based diet without enzymes. Birds fed 250 mg of phytase had the longest duodenal length while those fed 750 mg of phytase had the shortest. Longer jejunum was recorded for birds on acha – based diet without enzyme while those fed 750 mg of phytase had shorter length. Longer ilium and caeca was recorded for birds on maize –

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based diet and 250 mg of phytase, respectively. The variation did not follow any particular trend. This could suggest that acha – based diets supplemented with enzyme cannot adversely influence the length of GIT. Results for GIT pH indicated no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference by dietary treatments on the acidity and alkalinity of the intestinal segments. The pH of gizzard, proventriculus, jejunum and ilium was numerically similar ($P > 0.05$) for the treatment groups. Birds on maize – based diet had numerically ($P > 0.05$) higher pH value for duodenum and crop while acha – based diet had higher pH value for caeca.

Table 5: GIT Morphometry of broiler chickens fed acha – based diets

Parameters	Treatments					SEM
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	
<i>Intestinal weight (g)</i>						
GIT Weight	205.60	216.10	209.30	227.80	212.20	19.91
Duodenum	2.64	2.77	2.96	2.79	2.15	0.37
Jejunum	2.93	4.19	3.77	3.60	2.75	0.49
Ilium	21.04	24.26	20.90	19.90	20.14	3.13
Caeca	5.75	5.53	6.52	6.32	6.12	0.80
<i>Intestinal Length (cm)</i>						
Duodenum	12.67	14.00	14.67	14.33	12.33	0.91
Jejunum	16.67	18.00	17.67	17.00	15.33	1.41
Ilium	140.30	127.00	130.00	115.00	133.30	13.81
Caecum	27.30	30.70	32.00	31.00	30.00	2.53
<i>pH</i>						
Gizzard	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	0.00
Proventriculus	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	0.00
Duodenum	6.33	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	0.15
Jejunum	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	0.00
Crop	7.33	6.33	7.00	6.67	6.33	0.30
Ilium	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	0.00
Caeca	6.67	7.33	6.67	6.33	6.00	0.47

SEM = Standard error of mean

Organoleptic properties of broiler chicken meat fed acha – based diets

The organoleptic properties of chicken breast muscle based on treatments and cooking methods are presented in Tables 6 and 7, respectively. There was significant ($P < 0.05$) influences of dietary treatments and cooking methods on the sensory characteristics of

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chicken breast muscle. Colour, flavour, juiciness, number of chews, remains after chewing and tenderness were scored higher for birds fed 250 mg of phytase. Colour, flavour, juiciness, remain after chewing and tenderness were scored higher for microwaving followed by boiling and least with oven drying while number of chews was higher for boiling. This was an indication that diet and cooking methods have significant impact on the sensory properties of chicken breast muscle and that microwaving could enhance the overall acceptability of chicken breast muscle in broiler chickens.

Table 6: Organoleptic properties of chicken breast muscles based on dietary treatments

Parameter	Treatments					SEM
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	
Colour	2.56 ^{ab}	1.78 ^b	3.22 ^a	2.89 ^{ab}	2.44 ^{ab}	0.37
Flavour	3.67 ^a	2.22 ^c	3.67 ^a	2.89 ^b	3.11 ^{ab}	0.23
Juiciness	3.67 ^{ab}	3.00 ^{bc}	3.78 ^a	2.78 ^c	2.58 ^c	0.26
No. of chews	36.44 ^c	43.44 ^b	58.00 ^a	11.11 ^d	14.22 ^d	1.79
Remains after chewing	3.78 ^a	1.33 ^c	3.78 ^a	3.00 ^b	2.78 ^b	0.22
Tenderness	3.67 ^{ab}	2.89 ^{bc}	3.89 ^a	3.11 ^{abc}	2.56 ^c	0.26

^{abc} Means with different superscripts on the same row differ significantly (P<0.05)
SEM = Standard error of mean

Table 7: Effect of cooking methods on organoleptic properties of chicken breast muscle (meat)

Parameters	Treatments			SEM
	Microwaving	Boiling	Oven drying	
Colour	3.47 ^a	2.87 ^b	1.40 ^c	0.21
Flavour	3.47 ^a	3.27 ^a	2.60 ^b	0.20
Juiciness	3.33	3.00	3.13	0.23
No. of chews	32.10	33.90	31.90	4.93
Remains after chewing	3.13	2.93	2.79	0.29
Tenderness	3.53 ^a	2.80 ^b	3.33 ^{ab}	0.22

^{abc} Means with different superscripts on the same row differ significantly (P<0.05)
SEM = Standard error of mean

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Conclusion

Acha - based diet supplemented with 750 mg of Phytase for broiler chickens has shown positive responses in growth performance and carcass characteristics under the same environmental conditions as compared to the treatment groups.

Recommendation

For improved utilization of Acha and optimum broiler growth, carcass and meat quality, up to 750 mg of Phytase should be supplemented in broiler chicken diets.

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